

Analysis of Rice Food Logistic Readiness in West Java to Support Wars

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Abstract: Layered defense is needed to develop a dynamic strategic environment, one of which is war. War is carried out if the enemy manages to enter, seize, and control all or part of the territory of the Republic of Indonesia. Defense strategies in war need to be prepared. One of the logistics needed during the war was food logistics. Every region, including West Java, must have strong logistics in a war situation because when a war occurs, all people who focus on helping defense and other sectors such as food will be paralyzed. One type of staple food consumption is rice. Based on Central Bureau of Statistics Republic of Indonesia in 2020, the population in West Java is 48,274,162 people spread over 27 Regency/Municipality, and the total rice production is 5,180,201 tons. According to the regulation from the Ministry of Health Republic of Indonesia Number 28 of 2019 concerning the Recommended Nutritional Adequacy Rate for the Indonesian Society explained that the average Energy Adequacy Rate (AKE) for the Indonesian people is 2.100 kcal. This study aims to analyze the availability of rice food logistics and the ability of the West Java region to support the logistics needs of rice food in the event of a war in Indonesia. This study uses quantitative methods. The results showed that the daily requirement of rice per person is 125-157.5 grams or equivalent to 0.126-0.1575 kg. In support of the war, logistics readiness in the West Java region is 15 Regency/Municipality that are not ready, 2 Regency are ready but are within the consumption limit, and 10 Municipality are ready.

Keywords: Defense; rice food; logistic; war

I. Introduction

Dynamic strategic environmental conditions carry a complex spectrum of threats, challenges, and risks. Developing an unpredictable strategic environment needs to be addressed appropriately, quickly, and comprehensively. In drafting layered defense, defense strategies are implemented to ward off, overcome military and non-military threats, and carry out protracted wars [1]. TNI Doctrine Tri Dharma Eka Karma Chapter IV [2], states that protracted war is a form of enforcement carried out with guerrilla tactics if the enemy succeeds in entering, seizing, and controlling all or part of the territory of the Republic of Indonesia.

Defense strategies in protracted wars need to be prepared. In supporting the protracted war strategy, it is necessary to be prepared related to the elements of space, human resources, regional logistics, and strategic aspects based on the characteristics of their respective regions. In addition, there needs to be the utilization of natural resources, human resources, artificial resources, and other infrastructure facilities to become a backup and supporting capability for realizing a reliable state defense force.

Every war requires logistics. Logistics become the determinant of the success of the war. According to [3], logistics-related arrangements in combat aim to secure troops' needs in operation comprehensively. Efficient logistics operations will increase combat power. Logistics provision is vital in maintaining competitiveness in environmental uncertainty [4]. According to [5], in preparing its combat logistics, NATO deals with the transportation, retrieval, storage, and maintenance of weapons systems and includes the construction and operation of medical and health facilities and support services. In wars, logistics efficiency became a significant factor in the success of the battle. Wars require is not only weapons but also food and ammunition (Rahman and Hamid, 2019). Wars require many logistics because the war will last in the long run, so food availability becomes the key to winning the war. Every region, including West Java, is expected to have strong logistics in a war situation. As the war drags on, all the people focus on helping defense, while other sectors such as the economy and food will be crippled. One type of staple food that is commonly consumed is rice.

Based on data from Central Bureau of Statistics Republic of Indonesia in 2020, the total population in West Java is

48,274,162 people spread over 27 Regency/Municipality and total rice production in West Java province is 5,180,201 tons. According to [6], the average energy adequacy rate for the Indonesian people is 2.100 kcal per person per day at the level of consumption. It is necessary to analyze the availability of rice food and the ability of the West Java region to support the logistics needs of rice food in the event of a war in Indonesia.

II. Literature Review

2.1. Wars

Wars have occurred since ancient times and have colored the human journey from century to century. War has been a constant in human history. As [7] said, there is no peace in conditions of anarchy, and there will always be forms of anarchy as long as human nature is a variable in the system. According to [8], war is organized violence between groups fighting for specific goals using strategies.

War is a battle on a large scale where both parties involved in the battle try to direct all available forces to suppress the enemy until the opponent admits victory. War is a political continuation if diplomacy fails to resolve problems peacefully. So that war is the final way to solve the problem [9].

2.2. Defense Logistics

According to [10], logistics is positioning resources at the right time, place, cost, and quality. According to [11], logistics is the management of the flow of goods and services from the point of origin to the point of consumption to meet consumer needs. Logistics is the key in national defense, so it is necessary to effectively fulfill the need to adapt to unexpected demands due to unexpected threats [12].

Logistics is an important part of a war and is a vital component of the existence and functioning of a defense force. In general, the development of war logistics has changed dynamically throughout the ages, depending on fighting skills and technology development. Historically, logistical activities have always been associated with the creation, development, and support of war forces through the supply and maintenance of weapons and war equipment, supply of weapons, health care, food and water, and others [13].

War logistics support requires an approach to build a sustainable logistics system, adapt to new challenges, and support multiple objectives and missions in all conditions. Therefore, in times of war, it is necessary to have a logistics system that is flexible, dynamic, and strong enough to provide the necessary resources when they are needed, where they are needed, in the right quantities and in the required manner that is [13].

III. Research Methodology

The research method used is the quantitative method. The population in this study is the West Java region. The sample used is all Regency/Municipality in West Java. The step of this research are as follows:

1. Calculate total of calories needed from carbohydrates

$$\text{total calories from carbohydrates} = \% \text{needs} \times \text{average of AKE}$$

2. Calculate amount of cooked rice food needed

$$\text{amount of cooked rice needed} = \frac{\text{total calories needed} \times 100 \text{ gram}}{175 \text{ kkal}}$$

3. Conversion of food from cooked to raw

$$\text{uncooked weight} = \text{cooked weight} \times \text{conversion factor}$$

4. Calculate total consumption needs in a region

$$\text{total consumption needs} = \text{populations} \times \text{needs per person} \times \text{time}$$

5. Calculate logistical readiness of rice food in a region

$$\text{rice food logistics readiness} = \text{production availability} - \text{total consumption needs}$$

IV.Result and Discussion

Data on the need for rice consumption in a war is obtained from the regulation from Ministry of Health Republic of Indonesia Number 28 of 2019 concerning the Recommended Nutritional Adequacy Rate for the Indonesian Society. In Article 3 Section 2, it is explained that the average Energy Adequacy Rate (AKE) for the Indonesian people is 2.100 kcal per person per day at the level of consumption. Macronutrients are the main components that are the human body's primary source. There are three types of macronutrients in food: protein, carbohydrates, and fats [14]. According to WHO, the way to determine protein, fat and carbohydrate requirements is as follows: protein: 10-15% of total energy requirements; fat: 10-25% of total energy requirements; and carbohydrates: 60-75% of total energy requirements.

There is an upper limit, and a lower limit in meeting carbohydrate needs to be based on the WHO rules. The lower limit for meeting carbohydrate needs is 60% of total energy needs, while the upper limit for meeting carbohydrate needs is 75% of total energy needs. Then the calculation for the number of calories needed from carbohydrates is as follows:

$$\text{total calories from carbohydrates} = \% \text{needs} \times \text{average of AKE}$$

a. Lower limit:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{total calories from carbohydrates} &= 60\% \times 2.100 \text{ kcal} \\ &= 1.260 \text{ kcal/person/day} \end{aligned}$$

b. Upper limit:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{total calories from carbohydrates} &= 60\% \times 2.100 \text{ kcal} \\ &= 1.575 \text{ kcal/person/day} \end{aligned}$$

The lower limit of the number of calories needed from carbohydrates is 1260 kcal per person per day, it indicates the minimum need for carbohydrate intake needed by the body. While the upper limit on the number of calories needed from carbohydrates is 1575 kcal per person per day, it shows the body's maximum need for carbohydrate intake.

In this study, the food logistics analyzed was food logistics in rice. The Regulation of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, Number 14 of 2014 on Balanced Nutrition Guidelines, explained that the nutritional content value of 100 grams of cooked rice or equivalent to 0,75 glasses is 175 kcal. Then the calculation of carbohydrate needs in the form of cooked rice is as follows:

$$\text{amount of cooked rice needed} = \frac{\text{total calories needed} \times 100 \text{ gram}}{175 \text{ kcal}}$$

a. Lower limit:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{amount of cooked rice needed} &= \frac{1.260 \text{ kcal/person/day} \times 100 \text{ gram}}{175 \text{ kcal}} \\ &= 720 \text{ gram/person/day} \end{aligned}$$

b. Upper limit:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{amount of cooked rice needed} &= \frac{1.575 \text{ kcal/person/day} \times 100 \text{ gram}}{175 \text{ kcal}} \\ &= 900 \text{ gram/person/day} \end{aligned}$$

The lower limit of the need for carbohydrates in cooked rice is 720 grams per person per day, while the upper limit is 900 grams per person per day. The form of food to be analyzed is rice food, so it is necessary to calculate the conversion from the weight of cooked rice to the uncooked weight of rice. The calculation of the conversion from cooked rice weight to rice weight refers to the cooked-raw conversion calculation, namely the guidelines published by Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia in 2014 with the title is "Guidelines for Conversion of Uncooked-Cooked Weight, Edible Weight (BDD) and Ready-to-Eat and Snack Recipes". Then the calculation for the conversion of cooked rice weight to rice weight is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{uncooked weight} &= \text{cooked weight} \times \text{conversion factor} \\ \text{conversion factor cooked rice weight to rice} &= 0,4 \end{aligned}$$

a. Lower limit:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{uncooked weight} &= 720 \text{ gram/person/day} \times 0,4 \\ &= 299 \text{ gram/person/day} \\ &= 0,288 \text{ kg/person/day} \end{aligned}$$

b. Upper limit:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{uncooked weight} &= 900 \text{ gram/person/day} \times 0,4 \\ &= 360 \text{ gram/person/day} \\ &= 0,36 \text{ kg/person/day} \end{aligned}$$

Based on calculations, the lower limit of total carbohydrate needs in rice is 288 grams per person per day or

equivalent to 0,288 kg per person per day. At the same time, the upper limit of total carbohydrate needs in rice is 360 grams per person per day or equivalent to 0,36 kg per person per day.

The value of logistics readiness for each regency/municipality is calculated based on its consumption so that there is an upper and lower limit. All Regency/Municipality in West Java are calculated. Data on population and rice production are obtained from Central Bureau of Statistics Republic of Indonesia in 2020 An example of a calculation presented is Cianjur Regency.

$$\text{rice food logistics readiness} = \text{production availability} - \text{total consumption needs}$$

a. Example of calculating the need for total rice consumption for the lower limit in Cianjur Regency

$$\begin{aligned} \text{total consumption needs} &= 0,288 \text{ kg/person/day} \times 2.477.560 \text{ person} \times 365 \text{ day} \\ &= 260.441.107 \text{ kg in 365 day} \\ &= 260.441.107 \text{ kg in 1 year} \end{aligned}$$

b. Example of calculating the need for total rice consumption for the upper limit in Cianjur Regency

$$\begin{aligned} \text{total consumption needs} &= 0,36 \text{ kg/person/day} \times 2.477.560 \text{ person} \times 365 \text{ day} \\ &= 325.551.384 \text{ kg in 365 day} \\ &= 325.551.384 \text{ kg in 1 year} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{rice food logistics readiness} = \text{production availability} - \text{total consumption needs}$$

a. Example of calculating the rice food logistics readiness for the lower limit in Cianjur Regency

$$\begin{aligned} \text{rice food logistics readiness} &= 357.914.000 \text{ kg} - 260.441.107 \text{ kg} \\ &= 97.472.893 \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

b. Example of calculating the rice food logistics readiness for the upper limit in Cianjur Regency

$$\begin{aligned} \text{rice food logistics readiness} &= 357.914.000 \text{ kg} - 325.551.384 \text{ kg} \\ &= -67.637.384 \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

The results of the calculation of logistics readiness for all Regency/Municipality in the West Java region are presented in Table 1. The results of these calculations are mapped to facilitate analysis. For Regency/Municipality with positive upper and lower limits of logistics readiness, they are coloured green. Regency/Municipality with a negative upper limit on logistics readiness value and a positive lower limit will be coloured yellow. Regency/Municipality with a negative upper and lower limit for logistics readiness will be coloured red. Map of rice food logistics readiness in West Java is presented in Figure 1.

Based on the calculation results, 15 Regencies/Municipalities in the West Java region have not been able to fulfil their rice food logistics, including Bogor Regency, Bandung Regency, Garut Regency, Purwakarta Regency, Bekasi Regency, West Bandung Regency, Bogor Municipality, Sukabumi Municipality, Bandung Municipality, Cirebon Municipality, Bekasi Municipality, Depok Municipality, Cimahi Municipality, Tasikmalaya Municipality, and Banjar Municipality. 2 Regencies can only fulfil their rice food logistics with the condition of rice food consumption at the lower consumption limit adjusted to the Energy Adequacy Rate, namely Sukabumi Regency and Cirebon Regency. 10 Regencies have been able to fulfill their regional rice food logistics. The Regency include Cianjur Regency, Tasikmalaya Regency, Ciamis Regency, Kuningan Regency, Majalengka Regency, Sumedang Regency, Indramayu Regency, Subang Regency, Karawang Regency and Pangandaran Regency. Overall, rice food logistics in the West Java region have been able to support the war, but with the condition of rice food consumption at the lower consumption limit adjusted to the Energy Adequacy Rate

The conditions of a war require many logistics. Each region must have strong logistical resilience so that each region must be independent in its logistics availability, including food logistics. Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 7 of 1996 concerning Food states that the ultimate goal of food security is food sufficiency for households.

Based on the condition of the availability of rice food logistics in West Java and the protracted war situation, it is necessary to improve food logistics in several areas that still do not meet the availability standards. Efforts to improve food logistics need to be systematically structured between the government, society and industry. System development food logistics needs to consider several things: the condition of existing local resources.

Table 1The results of the calculation of logistics readiness for all Regency/Municipality in the West Java

No	Region	Population	Consumtion Needs (kg)		Rice Production 2020 (ton)	Rice Production 2020 (ton)	Readiness	
1	Bogor Regency	5.427.068	570.493.388	- 713.116.735	171.763	171.763.000	-398.730.388	- -541.353.735
2	Sukabumi Regency	2.725.450	286.499.304	- 358.124.130	299.582	299.582.000	13.082.696	- -58.542.130
3	Cianjur Regency	2.477.560	260.441.107	- 325.551.384	357.914	357.914.000	97.472.893	- 32.362.616
4	Bandung Regency	3.623.790	380.932.805	- 476.166.006	159.228	159.228.000	-221.704.805	- -316.938.006
5	Garut Regency	2.585.607	271.799.008	- 339.748.760	244.116	244.116.000	-27.683.008	- -95.632.760
6	Tasikmalaya Regency	1.865.203	196.070.139	- 245.087.674	255.287	255.287.000	59.216.861	- 10.199.326
7	Ciamis Regency	1.229.069	129.199.733	- 161.499.667	162.466	162.466.000	33.266.267	- 966.333
8	Kuningan Regency	1.167.686	122.747.152	- 153.433.940	159.321	159.321.000	36.573.848	- 5.887.060
9	Cirebon Regency	2.270.621	238.687.680	- 298.359.599	285.576	285.576.000	46.888.320	- -12.783.599
10	Majalengka Regency	1.305.476	137.231.637	- 171.539.546	325.363	325.363.000	188.131.363	- 153.823.454
11	Sumedang Regency	1.152.507	121.151.536	- 151.439.420	176.476	176.476.000	55.324.464	- 25.036.580
12	Indramayu Regency	1.834.434	192.835.702	- 241.044.628	783.233	783.233.000	590.397.298	- 542.188.372
13	Subang Regency	1.595.320	167.700.038	- 209.625.048	557.709	557.709.000	390.008.962	- 348.083.952
14	Purwakarta Regency	997.869	104.895.989	- 131.119.987	91.897	91.897.000	-12.998.989	- -39.222.987
15	Karawang Regency	2.439.085	256.396.615	- 320.495.769	624.992	624.992.000	368.595.385	- 304.496.231
16	Bekasi Regency	3.113.017	327.240.347	- 409.050.434	289.611	289.611.000	-37.629.347	- -119.439.434
17	Bandung Barat Regency	1.788.336	187.989.880	- 234.987.350	94.587	94.587.000	-93.402.880	- -140.400.350
18	Pangandaran Regency	423.667	44.535.875	- 55.669.844	89.039	89.039.000	44.503.125	- 33.369.156
19	Bogor Municipality	1.043.070	109.647.518	- 137.059.398	87	87.000	-109.560.518	- -136.972.398
20	Sukabumi Municipality	346.325	36.405.684	- 45.507.105	8.349	8.349.000	-28.056.684	- -37.158.105
21	Bandung Municipality	2.444.160	256.930.099	- 321.162.624	3.906	3.906.000	-253.024.099	- -317.256.624
22	Cirebon Municipality	333.303	35.036.811	- 43.796.014	592	592.000	-34.444.811	- -43.204.014
23	Bekasi Municipality	2.543.676	267.391.221	- 334.239.026	1.564	1.564.000	-265.827.221	- -332.675.026
24	Depok Municipality	2.056.335	216.161.935	- 270.202.419	109	109.000	-216.052.935	- -270.093.419
25	Cimahi Municipality	568.400	59.750.208	- 74.687.760	251	251.000	-59.499.208	- -74.436.760
26	Tasikmalaya Municipality	716.155	75.282.214	- 94.102.767	20.883	20.883.000	-54.399.214	- -73.219.767
27	Banjar Municipality	200.973	21.126.282	- 26.407.852	16.300	16.300.000	-4.826.282	- -10.107.852
Sum		48.274.162	5.074.579.909	- 6.343.224.887	5.180.201	5.180.201.000	105.621.091	- -1.163.023.887

Figure 1. Map of rice food logistics readiness in West Java

V. Conclusion

The need for food logistics that must be prepared in a protracted war is 2.100 kcal. This is in accordance with the regulation from the Ministry of Health Republic of Indonesia Number 28 of 2019 concerning the Recommended Nutritional Adequacy Rate for the Indonesian Society. Based on the calculations that have been made, the need for rice per person per day is 126-157,5 gram or 0,126-0,1575 kg. In the condition of war, the logistical readiness of rice food in each region varies, there are 15 Regencies/Municipalities that are not ready, 2 Regencies are ready but are within the consumption limit, and 10 Regencies/Municipalities are ready.

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